

Evidence of total suspended solids control by *Mugil liza* reared in an integrated system with pacific white shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* using biofloc technology

Mariana Holanda^a, Gabriel Santana^a, Plínio Furtado^a, Ricardo Vieira Rodrigues^{a,c}, Vinícius Ronzani Cerqueira^d, Luís André Sampaio^{a,c}, Wilson Wasielesky Jr.^{a,b}, Luis Henrique Poersch^{a,*}

^a Programa de Pós-Graduação em Aquicultura, Instituto de Oceanografia, Universidade Federal do Rio Grande - FURG, Rua do Hotel, n°2, Cassino, Rio Grande, RS CEP: 96210-030, Brazil

^b Laboratório de Carcinocultura, Instituto de Oceanografia, Universidade Federal do Rio Grande - FURG, Brazil

^c Laboratório de Piscicultura Estuarina e Marinha, Instituto de Oceanografia, Universidade Federal do Rio Grande - FURG, Brazil

^d Laboratório de Piscicultura Marinha, Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, SC, Brazil

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:
Biofloc
IMTA system
Mullet
Nitrification
Sustainability

ABSTRACT

The biofloc culture system (BFT) allows for the production of aquatic animals at higher stocking densities compared to conventional aquaculture systems and it has been proven to be efficient for shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*) and mullet (*Mugil liza*) rearing. Accumulation of nutrients enhances the natural productivity of the system, thus the concentration of total suspended solids (TSS) tends to accumulate during the production cycle, which can deteriorate the water quality and performance of the animals produced. Integrated multi trophic aquaculture (IMTA) can be performed in single or multi tank systems, depending on the interaction of the different species being cultured. The present study aimed to reduce TSS concentration by integrating juvenile mullet into a shrimp BFT system, through the consumption of these solids by the mullet. Three different treatments were used: shrimp monoculture (MONO), single tank (SING -shrimp and mullet cultured in the same tank) and IMTA multi tank (MULT- shrimp and mullet cultured in different tanks). The performance of shrimp was impaired in the SING treatment, while mullet had their best zootechnical performance in this treatment. The presence of the fish modified the nitrification even with the use of biofloc inoculum. The presence of mullet, regardless of the IMTA system used, resulted in lower biofloc concentrations, compared to the monoculture of shrimp, thus confirming that mullet can be used to control solids concentrations originating from shrimp production in a BFT system.

1. Introduction

The continuous growth of aquaculture, including production of shrimp and carnivorous fish in intensive systems, leads to questions related to its sustainability (Naylor et al., 2009; Perdikaris et al., 2016). Biofloc Technology (BFT) has been developed and adopted mainly by shrimp and tilapia farmers focused on increased productivity, coupled to a greater concern with the environmental impacts of aquaculture through nutrient recycling, as well as wanting to minimize water use (Wasielesky et al., 2006; Azim and Little, 2008). The reduction in the emission of effluents with the utilization of BFT systems reduces the risks

of contamination and dissemination of diseases (Ekasari et al., 2014). The microbial community that contributes to the maintenance of adequate water quality, is also a source of supplementary food for the cultivated animals (Lara et al., 2017). The formation of the microbial community occurs due to the alteration of the carbon:nitrogen ratio in the water (elevation to 15:1) due to the accumulation of nutrients from the excretion of cultured animals, and decomposition of uneaten food in the system, coupled to intense and constant aeration (Ebeling et al., 2006). This way, organic matter and nutrients that would be disposed of to the environment in conventional farms, through water renewal, now remain in the system and are recycled by microorganisms

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: lpoesch@mikrus.com.br (L.H. Poersch).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aqrep.2020.100479>

Received 11 October 2019; Received in revised form 29 August 2020; Accepted 5 September 2020

Available online 21 September 2020

2352-5134/© 2020 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

(Krummenauer et al., 2014).

Despite the benefits of BFT systems, limited or no water renewal results in the accumulation of total suspended solids (TSS) and nutrients (especially nitrate and phosphate), which in high levels can be harmful to the cultured animals (Ray et al., 2010; Gaona et al., 2011). The constant increase of TSS in a BFT system is a consequence of the increase of microbial biomass, which takes advantage of the carbon and the nitrogenous compounds from organic fertilizations and excreta of the animals. During pacific white shrimp *L. vannamei* production in BFT systems, it is recommended to maintain the levels of solids between 10–14 mL L⁻¹ for settleable solids (SS), 250–350 mg L⁻¹ for total suspended solids (TSS) and 75 and 200 NTU for turbidity (Samocha and Prangnell, 2019). These solids can turn into an environmental problem if not properly discarded. The excess of suspended material deteriorates water quality and can also cause occlusion of the gills inducing the animals to hypoxia, consequently harming shrimp growth. It also raises energy costs to keep the levels of dissolved oxygen within appropriate limits for the species (Avnimelech, 1999; Crab et al., 2012; Gaona et al., 2017). Therefore, in order to keep TSS within adequate levels, they are commonly removed from the tanks by mechanical clarifiers, which act as particle decanters (Gaona et al., 2011).

The control of TSS can also be performed by the adoption of Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA), since this method integrates several species of organisms that can use the solid or dissolved residues present in the production system (Chopin et al., 2001; Troell et al., 2009; Martínez-Espiñeira et al., 2015; Legarda et al., 2019; Poli et al., 2019). In general, IMTA includes inorganic extractive species (macro or micro-algae) and/or organic extractive species (mollusks and low trophic level fish) in the production of carnivorous fish and shrimp (Neori et al., 2007; Ekasari et al., 2014; Granada et al., 2016; David et al., 2017). With the appropriate composition of species in an IMTA, reduction of excess nutrients and organic matter generated in the system can be achieved.

The mullet (*M. liza*) is a promising species to IMTA, being iliofagic, consuming mainly the vegetal matter removed from effluent or sand (Oliveira and Soares, 1996). These fish are able to convert the potential energy of the waste into energy that can be used at other trophic levels and are also potential consumers of excess solids from the BFT system, acting as a filter for the system. Some studies have already reported the production of Mugilidae in BFT systems (Rocha et al., 2012; Da Silva et al., 2013) as well as their use in integrated production with other species of fish (Melo et al., 2016; Shpigel et al., 2016), in floating cages (Ghosh et al., 2016), and even with shrimp *L. vannamei* (Hoang et al., 2018). Therefore, the present study aimed to evaluate the feasibility of IMTA composed of mullet and shrimp grown in a BFT system, evaluating the best spatial arrangement for both species, such as if being reared together in the same tank or alone in separate tanks, and if the presence of mullet reduces the concentration of total suspended solids in the system.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study location and origin of the animals

This study was conducted at the Marine Aquaculture Station (EMA) of the Institute of Oceanography of the Federal University of Rio Grande - FURG, located at Cassin Beach in Rio Grande, RS, Southern Brazil. The juvenile mullet used in this experiment were produced at the Laboratory of Marine Fish Culture of the Federal University of Santa Catarina (Brazil) according to the protocol described in Cerqueira et al. (2017). Prior to the experiment, juveniles (8.8 ± 2.1 g) were acclimated in a BFT system for two weeks. Juvenile shrimp (1.2 ± 0.52 g) were reared in a greenhouse using a BFT system at the Laboratory of Shrimp Culture (FURG). This experiment was approved by FURG's Ethical and Animal Welfare Committee (Process number 23116.005895/2016-42).

2.2. Systems and experimental design

The experiment lasted for 31 days. The experimental design consisted of three treatments in triplicate (3 × 3): shrimp monoculture (MONO), IMTA single tank (SING) -shrimp and mullet cultured in the same tank; and IMTA multi tank (MULT) - shrimp and mullet cultured in different tanks. Shrimp were reared at a density of 204 shrimp m⁻³ and mullet at a density of 100 mullet m⁻³. In the last treatment, the water from the mullet tanks was constantly circulated to the shrimp tanks (flow rate 720 L h⁻¹) with the aid of a pump (Sarlo Better®, SB 1000C, Brazil, 13 W) and returned to the mullet tanks by gravity. The polyethylene experimental tanks had a water volume of 220 L and a bottom area of 0.36 m². The tanks were in a closed room with artificial light, covered with a polyethylene screen to prevent shrimp and fish escaping, and the photoperiod was 12:12 h light:dark. Water was constantly aerated through air stones (two air stones per tank with 3.4 cm² and 13 cm in length), in order to aid the suspension of the biofloc and to keep adequate dissolved oxygen concentration. Water temperature was kept constant using heaters with thermostats (Stealth, ETP250, USA, 250 W).

2.3. Biological material and feeding

The experimental units were stocked with mature bioflocs, corresponding to 20 % of the volume of the experimental tank (initial concentration ±80 mg L⁻¹ of TSS and ±1.7 mg L⁻¹ of nitrate), from a *L. vannamei* cultivation in a greenhouse, molasses with a carbon source was used in initial phases of cultivation for ammonia control. The matrix tank had a volume of 70 m³, with the already established nitrification, through the detection of nitrate.

All animals (shrimp and mullet) were fed with commercial dry diets, during the first week with Potimar 40 J with 40 % crude protein and later on they were fed with Potimar 38 Active with 38 % crude protein (1.6 mm), both produced by Guabi Nutrição e Saúde Animal S.A. (Brazil). Shrimp were fed twice a day (9:00 a.m. and 5:00 p.m.) following the methodology described by Jory (2001), while mullet were underfed (once a day with 1% of fish biomass, stimulating the mullet to feed on the bioflocs) throughout the experimental period. The feed rates of the shrimp and fish were adjusted biweekly according to growth sampling during the study.

2.4. Water quality analyses and management

Dissolved oxygen, temperature and pH were monitored twice a day prior to feeding the organisms. Temperature and dissolved oxygen were measured using an oximeter (YSI, model Pro-20, USA) and pH was measured with a pHmeter (Mettler Toledo, FEP20, Brazil). The salinity was verified with an optical refractometer (ATC, RTP-20ATC, Brazil).

Total ammonia nitrogen (TAN) and nitrite were measured daily according to the methodology described by UNESCO (1983) and American Public Health Association (APHA) (2017), Bendschneider and Robinson (1952), respectively. Turbidity and TSS were analyzed at 4-day intervals. Turbidity was measured by reading a portable turbidimeter (Hach®, 2100 P, Portugal) and TSS following American Public Health Association (APHA) (2017). Alkalinity was measured twice a week (American Public Health Association (APHA), 2017). Nitrate and orthophosphate were measured once a week, following the methodologies of Aminot and Chaussepied (1983). When pH values dropped from 7.2 and alkalinity values dropped from 120 mg CaCO₃ L⁻¹, they were corrected with hydrated lime [Ca (OH)₂] accordingly to Furtado et al. (2014). Fresh water was added weekly to compensate for the evaporation of the tanks. The water quality parameters, and addition of hydrated lime in the MULT treatment tanks were measured in both tanks and the data presented are an average of them.

2.4.1. Growth performance

Shrimp (15 shrimp/tank) and fish (10 fish/tank) growth was

estimated biweekly using a digital scale with 0.01 g precision (Marte Científica, AD 2000, Brazil). Before mullet were weighed, they were anesthetized in a benzocaine bath (50 mg L^{-1}) as described by Braz et al. (2017). At the end of the experimental period, all remaining animals (shrimp and fish) and systems (shrimp plus fish) were counted to determine survival. The parameters analyzed were:

- (1) Survival (%) = (final number/ initial number) $\times 100$;
- (2) Final mean weight (g): final weight of animals (g) / total number of animals;
- (3) Total biomass (g): \sum final weight of animals (g);
- (4) Weekly growth gain (g week^{-1}): ((final mean weight (g) - initial mean weight (g)) / weeks of culture);
- (5) Apparent Feed conversion ratio (FCR) = offered feed (g)/(final biomass (g) - initial biomass (g));
- (6) Productivity (kg m^{-3}): [(final biomass (kg) - initial biomass (kg)) $\times 1000$] / useful tank volume (L).

For system productivity calculations, the total volume considered in the MULT treatment was 0.44 m^3 and the total volume considered in the SING and MONO treatments was 0.22 m^3 .

2.5. Statistical analysis

All data was analyzed by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), except the zootechnical performance data of the mullet that was analyzed by the *t*-test. Homoscedasticity and normality were analyzed by the Levene test and the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test, respectively. The Tukey test was applied when significant differences were detected ($P < 0.05$). Survival results were arcsine transformed prior to the analysis (Zar, 2010).

3. Results

3.1. Water quality

There was no significant difference in temperature, dissolved oxygen or salinity between treatments. The pH and alkalinity showed a significant difference between the treatments, with the MULT treatment presenting higher means, while the MONO and SING treatments presented lower means, with no significant difference among them.

TSS and turbidity were higher in MONO treatments and lower in MULT. There was a significant TSS value difference between treatments over time, starting from the 10th day, where the MULT treatment followed with lower values until the last day of experiment (Fig. 1).

As for nutrients, the averages of ammonia, nitrate and phosphate did not differ significantly between the treatments, while nitrite was significantly higher in the SING and MULT treatments compared to MONO (Table 1).

During the experimental period, differences in TAN, nitrite, nitrate and phosphate values were observed. TAN values oscillated during the experimental period in all treatments with significant differences on the 4th day, with higher TAN in the SING and MULT treatments when compared to the MONO treatment on the 10th day, with differences between all treatments, with the MULT treatment presenting higher values and MONO presenting lower TAN values. On the 22nd and 24th days, the TAN treatments also showed a significant difference, with the SING and MULT treatments showing higher values and the MONO treatment showing lower values. On the other days no significant differences were found among the treatments (Fig. 2A)

There was a significant difference in mean nitrite values during the experimental period. The MONO treatment presented significantly lower values throughout the experimental period, with the exception of the 4th and 10th days, where values were equal to those of the MULT treatment. Up to the 14th day the SING treatment presented higher values of nitrite than the other treatments and from the 18th day, the

Fig. 1. Mean concentrations of total suspended solids (TSS) (mg L^{-1}) and turbidity (NTU), over the 31-day experimental period, in the different treatments: monoculture (Monoculture of *L. vannamei*); IMTA ST (Integrated culture of *L. vannamei* and *M. liza* in same tanks); and IMTA DT (Integrated culture of *L. vannamei* and *M. liza* in different tanks). Data is presented as mean \pm standard error ($n = 3$). Different letters represents significant differences ($P < 0.05$) among treatments after One-way ANOVA.

values of nitrite of the MULT treatment began to rise until the end of the experiment (Fig. 2B).

As for nitrate, from the 8th day on there was a difference between the mean values in the SING and MULT treatments, when compared to the MONO, with an increase in the SING treatment, followed by the MONO treatment and the MULT treatment, with lower nitrate values on the 30th day of experiment (Fig. 2C).

The phosphate values only showed a significant difference on the last day of the experiment, the MULT treatment having higher values and the MONO and SING treatments having lower values, without significant differences between them (Fig. 2D).

3.2. Shrimp and mullet performance

Survival was lower in the MONO treatment and higher in the SING and MULT treatments, with no significant difference between them. The mean final weight and WWG (weekly growth gain) were higher in the MONO and MULT treatments. The FCR (feed conversion ratio) showed no significant difference among the treatments. The final biomass was higher in the MULT treatment and lower in the SING treatment. The yield was higher in the MONO treatment and lower in the MULT and

Table 1

Water quality parameters (mean ± standard deviation) during the experiment in the different treatments: shrimp monoculture (MONO), IMTA single tank (SING)-shrimp and mullet cultured in the same tank; and IMTA multi tank (MULT) -shrimp and mullet cultured in different tanks.

	Monoculture	SING	MULT
Temperature °C	28.0 ± 0.5	27.8 ± 0.6	28.6 ± 0.6
(Min-Max)	(26.5–28.5)	(25.3–29.1)	(26.6–29.1)
DO (mg L ⁻¹)	6.15 ± 0.35	6.18 ± 0.35	6.09 ± 0.34
(Min-Max)	(5.81–6.51)	(5.73–6.70)	(5.86–6.28)
Salinity (ppt)	22.50 ± 1.37	22.67 ± 1.21	22.17 ± 1.33
(Min-Max)	(20.6–22.3)	(20.6–23.0)	(21.0–23.0)
pH	8.15 ± 0.15	8.14 ± 0.11	8.22 ± 0.12
(Min-Max)	(7.86–8.27)	(7.9–8.28)	(8.09–8.31)
Alkalinity (mg CaCO ₃ L ⁻¹)	123.27 ± 10.28	120 ± 9.82	131.83 ± 9.69
(Min-Max)	(120–150)	(105–135)	(115–140)
TSS (mg L ⁻¹)	190.28 ± 103.32 ^a	142.11 ± 63.69 ^b	89.79 ± 18.32 ^c
(Min-Max)	(80–325)	(80–245)	(60–110)
Turbidity (NTU)	88.0 ± 60.9 ^a	71.5 ± 42.5 ^b	40.9 ± 14.1 ^c
(Min-Max)	(17.2–170)	(18.8–106)	(20.8–54.2)
TAN (mg L ⁻¹)	0.07 ± 0.06	0.08 ± 0.13	0.05 ± 0.03
(Min-Max)	(0.01–0.08)	(0.01–0.14)	(0.01–0.12)
NO ₂ -N (mg L ⁻¹)	0.07 ± 0.04 ^a	0.44 ± 0.23 ^b	0.48 ± 0.35 ^b
(Min-Max)	(0.09–0.11)	(0.17–0.82)	(0.12–1.54)
NO ₃ -N (mg L ⁻¹)	13.15 ± 12.22	18.27 ± 14.19	12.55 ± 9.36
(Min-Max)	(1–37)	(2–40)	(1–30)
PO ₄ ³⁻ (mg L ⁻¹)	1.34 ± 0.85	1.75 ± 1.33	1.94 ± 1.69
(Min-Max)	(0.56–4.2)	(0.47–4.2)	(0.67–5.1)

Different letters in the same line represents significant differences (P < 0.05) among treatments after One-way ANOVA followed Tukey's Test for shrimp and Sistem (shrimp plus mullet) and test for mullet. DO (dissolved oxygen), TSS (Total suspended solids), TAN (total ammonia). (Min-Max) = interval between the minimum and maximum values observed in each treatment. n = 3.

SING treatments, without significant difference between them, when the calculations were made considering 0.44 m³ of the volume of the MULT treatment. When the volume of the MULT treatment was considered with the same volume as the other treatments (0.22 m³), the MONO and MULT treatments presented higher productivity, without significant differences between them, while the SING treatment presented lower yield.

As for the system (shrimp plus mullet), the total final biomass was higher in the MULT treatment and lower in the MONO treatment, the total yield was higher in the SING treatment, and lower in the MONO treatment. FCR did not show significant difference among the treatments (Table 2).

4. Discussion

4.1. Water quality

The water quality parameters of the experiment were within the recommendation for the proper growth of *L. vannamei* and *M. liza* (Legarda et al., 2019; Poersch et al., 2007; Wasielesky et al., 2006). The presence of mullet both in the same pond (SING) and in separate tanks (MULT) did not affect dissolved oxygen levels, a limiting parameter for the proper growth of cultured animals, but the pH and alkalinity were higher in the MULT treatment, where shrimp and mullet were in separate tanks. Alkalinity and pH have a direct relation with nitrification, as the nitrifying bacteria use inorganic carbon from alkalinity in their metabolism (Ebeling et al., 2006). In the MULT treatment, nitrification was impaired in some way, since the nitrite values were higher and the final value of nitrate was lower, it is likely that this is an explanation for the lower levels of pH and alkalinity in this treatment.

Although nitrite values are well below the toxicity level for shrimp (Lin and Chen, 2003) or mullet (Sampaio et al., 2002), a relationship is

Fig. 2. Mean concentrations of total ammoniacal nitrogen (TAN) (mg L⁻¹), nitrite (NO₂-N) (mg L⁻¹) and nitrate (NO₃-N) (mg L⁻¹), over the 31-day experimental period, in the different treatments: monoculture (Monoculture of *L. vannamei*); IMTA ST (Integrated culture of *L. vannamei* and *M. liza* in same tanks); and IMTA DT (Integrated culture of *L. vannamei* and *M. liza* in different tanks). Data is presented as mean ± standard error (n = 3). Different letters represents significant differences (P < 0.05) among treatments after One-way ANOVA.

Table 2

Zootechnical performance (mean \pm standard deviation) of *L. vannamei* and *M. liza* during the experiment in the different treatments: shrimp monoculture (MONO), IMTA single tank (SING) - shrimp and mullet cultured in the same tank; and IMTA multi tank (MULT) - shrimp and mullet cultured in different tanks.

	MONO	SING	MULT
Shrimp performance			
Survival (%)	84.4 \pm 2.2 ^b	95.5 \pm 5.8 ^a	96.6 \pm 4.7 ^a
Mean final weight (g)	4.51 \pm 0.22 ^a	2.31 \pm 0.25 ^b	4.87 \pm 0.6 ^a
FCR	1.8 \pm 0.09	1.3 \pm 0.05	1.4 \pm 0.05
WWG (g week ⁻¹)	0.83 \pm 0.06 ^a	0.28 \pm 0.06 ^b	0.92 \pm 0.15 ^a
Final biomass (kg)	0.17 \pm 0.05 ^b	0.10 \pm 0.01 ^c	0.21 \pm 0.02 ^a
Yield [#] (kg m ⁻³)	0.77 \pm 0.02 ^a	0.44 \pm 0.02 ^b	0.52 \pm 0.03 ^b
Yield* (kg m ⁻³)	0.77 \pm 0.02 ^a	0.44 \pm 0.02 ^b	0.94 \pm 0.1 ^a
Mullet performance			
Survival (%)	–	92.59 \pm 3.21	100 \pm 0
Mean final weight (g)	–	15.97 \pm 0.62 ^a	11.07 \pm 0.23 ^b
FCR	–	1.5 \pm 0.15 ^a	1.2 \pm 0.08 ^b
WWG (g week ⁻¹)	–	1.79 \pm 0.15 ^a	0.57 \pm 0.06 ^b
Final biomass (kg)	–	0.27 \pm 0.01 ^a	0.20 \pm 0.04 ^b
Yield (kg m ⁻³) [#]	–	1.2 \pm 0.05 ^a	0.5 \pm 0.01 ^b
Yield (kg m ⁻³) [*]	–	1.2 \pm 0.01 ^a	0.9 \pm 0.01 ^b
Shrimp plus Mullet			
Total final biomass (kg)	0.17 \pm 0.05 ^c	0.36 \pm 0.05 ^b	0.41 \pm 0.01 ^a
Total yield (kg m ⁻³)	0.77 \pm 0.02 ^c	1.65 \pm 0.02 ^a	1.03 \pm 0.02 ^b
FCR	1.52 \pm 0.21	1.48 \pm 0.05	1.35 \pm 0.12

WWG: Weekly growth gain; FCR: Feed conversion ratio. Different letters in the same line represents significant differences ($P < 0.05$) among treatments after One-way ANOVA followed Tukey's Test for shrimp and Sistem (shrimp plus mullet) and test for mullet. # Productivity calculated using 0.22 m³ for the MONO and SING treatments, and 0.44 m³ for the MULT treatment. *Productivity calculated using 0.22 m³ for all treatments. n = 3.

noted between the presence of mullet in the system and instability in nitrite levels. A 20 % biofloc inoculum was used, as recommended by Krummenauer et al. (2014), from a culture of *L. vannamei* that already had nitrate detection, i.e. nitrification was occurring and the inoculum presented bacteria from both the Ammonia-Oxidizing Bacteria (AOB) and the Nitrite-Oxidizing Bacteria (NOB). Only in the MONO treatment, the nitrogen compounds followed a pattern of use of bioflocs with low levels of ammonia and nitrite, as described by Krummenauer et al. (2014).

The presence of mullet in the SING and MULT treatments possibly affected the nitrifying bacteria in some way. There are some assumptions: the swimming of the fish or even the presence of the pump that returned the water to the shrimp tanks, may have ruptured the bioflocs, exposing their nuclei to more oxygenated zones and inhibiting the metabolism of NOB, since the nitrifying bacteria are distributed in bioflocs according to the oxygen rate, which is a determining factor for their growth and proper functioning. The NOB are found in greater abundance in the internal areas of the bioflocs, being more sensitive to higher concentrations of oxygen and the AOB inhabit the outermost layer, as they are more resistant to higher levels of oxygen (Carvalho et al., 2006; Figueroa and Silverstein, 1992; Vlaeminck et al., 2010).

Another hypothesis to consider is that mullet fed on the bioflocs in such a way that the nitrifying bacteria were affected by the lack of substrate. This second hypothesis is based on the low values of TSS and lower final values of nitrate in the MULT treatment. Possibly the feed ratio of 1% in relation to biomass in the MULT treatment was insufficient to maintain a balance of TSS production by the system and TSS consumption by mullet.

4.2. Solids intake

The concentration of TSS for shrimp culture in a BFT system should be maintained between 250 and 350 mg L⁻¹ (Samocha and Prangnell, 2019). In the present study, TSS levels did not exceed 350 mg L⁻¹ in the MONO treatment, where values were higher, probably due to the short

experimental period. When mullet were present, TSS values were controlled in relation to the MONO treatment, even though there was a higher biomass in these treatments (shrimp + fish), which indicates that mullet fed on the bioflocs. In the MULT treatment, TSS was lower than in the SING treatment, possibly due to the higher consumption of solids by the mullet. In the MULT treatment, mullet were in separate ponds consuming only the feed offered (1% of biomass), whereas in the SING treatment, because mullet were in the same pond as shrimp, they had access to shrimp feed in addition to their own feed. This may have contributed to the higher consumption of TSS by the mullet in the MULT treatment. This hypothesis is strengthened by the lower FCR of the mullet in the MULT treatment.

Throughout the production cycle, excess bioflocs need to be removed from the culture tanks because excess suspended solids can cause fish and shrimp gills to occlude (Hargreaves, 2006), in addition, bioflocs also consume oxygen, so the excess bioflocs lead to higher oxygen demand from the system and consequently, cost increases. Therefore, when mullet consume excess solids from the BFT system, we have a solution to a problem, transforming aquaculture residue into animal protein.

Similar results of consumption of biofloc by mullet were observed when produced in integrated cultures with *L. vannamei* (Legarda et al., 2019) or with other species (Larson and Shanks, 1996; Shpigel et al., 2016).

4.3. Shrimp and mullet performance

The survival of the shrimp in the MONO treatment was lower than in other treatments, likely indicating some protective effect of the presence of fish in relation to shrimp. The presence of mullet negatively affected the zootechnical performance of the shrimp in the SING treatment, probably due to the stress caused by the increased density from the presence of fish, together with the small size of the experimental unit. The SING treatment had the best zootechnical performance for the mullet, indicating that mullet may have consumed shrimp feed in addition to their own in this treatment, which was reflected in a lower consumption of biofloc in this treatment. The FCR of the mullet in this study was similar to that reported by Legarda et al. (2019) (FCR = 1.34 \pm 0.12), the authors also commented that the feed conversion of mullet in a traditional system exceeds, up to 4 times, the value of FCR found in their study.

Melo et al. (2016) also reported competition for food and observed signs of stress for *L. schmitti* in an integrated culture with mullet, as it was observed that the shrimp swam close to the wall of the tanks, which can characterize stress caused by the presence of mullet.

When only the shrimp tank is considered for the calculation of the yield, the MONO and MULT treatments have equal yields. When considering the volume of the MULT treatment as the volume of shrimp and fish tanks, the MONO treatment has the highest yield, which is still low when considering shrimp cultures in a BFT system (Poli et al., 2019; Reis et al., 2019), probably due to the short time and size of the experimental units. The results of this experiment show that the separation of the shrimp pond from the fish pond brings a zootechnical advantage to the farmed shrimp, and an environmental advantage due to the higher consumption of biofloc, but an economic disadvantage in terms of area used for production.

Land-based IMTA are mostly closed systems, such as the one proposed in this study, which allows the control of nutrient-rich waste, thus decreasing the negative environmental impacts of aquaculture (Chopin et al., 2001; Kerrigan and Suckling, 2018). Coupling a BFT system – which by itself uses minimal or no water renewal and, hence, generates low effluent discharge into the environment – to IMTA, can make aquaculture more environmentally friendly. In this system, mullet consumed excess biofloc in the BFT system, which transforms this residue into animal protein with low feed costs, and still provides a marketable by-product for the farmer.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrated that the integrated cultivation of *L. vannamei* and *M. Liza* is feasible on a pilot scale. The mullet proved to be efficient in the consumption and maintenance of TSS levels in the integrated shrimp system. In the MULT treatment, mullet consumed the TSS to the point of impairing the nitrification of the biofloc system. In terms of mullet biofloc consumption and shrimp zootechnical performance, the best spatial system for integrated mullet culture is the MULT system, with fish and shrimp in separate tanks. As far as the yield of the system is concerned, the best is the cultivation of shrimp and mullet in the same tank, as in the SING treatment. New studies are needed to find a better ratio of shrimp to mullet, as well as new feed rates that allow the consumption of biofloc by mullet and proper growth of the shrimp in the same pond. Studies on a larger scale that also aim at economic analysis of the system are encouraged.

AUTHORSHIP STATEMENT

All persons who meet authorship criteria are listed as authors, and all authors certify that they have participated sufficiently in the work to take public responsibility for the content, including participation in the concept, design, analysis, writing, or revision of the manuscript. Furthermore, each author certifies that this material or similar material has not been and will not be submitted to or published in any other publication before.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

The authors are grateful for the financial support provided by the European Community (AquaVitae Project – H2020 SC2), National Council for Scientific and Technological Development (CNPq) and Coordination for the Improvement of Higher- Level Personnel (CAPES). Cerqueira, V.R., Sampaio, L.A., Wasielesky, W.J., and Poersch, L.H., are research fellows of CNPq. Special thanks to GUABI Animal Health and Nutrition SA for donating the commercial diets.

References

American Public Health Association (APHA), 2017. Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Waste Water, 23th ed. American Public Health Association, AWWA, WPCF, New York.

Aminot, A., Chaussepied, M., 1983. Manuel des analyses chimiques en milieu marin. CNEXO, Brest, p. 395p.

Avnimelech, Y., 1999. Carbon r nitrogen ratio as a control element in aquaculture systems. *Aquaculture* 227–235.

Azim, M.E., Little, D.C., 2008. The biofloc technology (BFT) in indoor tanks: water quality, biofloc composition, and growth and welfare of Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). *Aquaculture* 283, 29–35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2008.06.036>.

Bendschneider, K., Robinson, R.J., 1952. A new spectrophotometric method for the determination of nitrite in sea water. *J. Mar. Res.* 11, 87–96.

Braz, R., da, S., Silva, I., de, O., Tesser, M.B., Sampaio, L.A., Rodrigues, R.V., 2017. Benzocafina, MS-222, eugenol e mentol como anestésicos para juvenis de tainha *Mugil liza*. *Bol. do Inst. Pesca* 43, 605–613. <https://doi.org/10.20950/1678-2305.2017v43n4p605>.

Carvalho, G., Meyer, R.L., Yuan, Z., Keller, J., 2006. Differential distribution of ammonia- and nitrite-oxidising bacteria in flocs and granules from a nitrifying/denitrifying sequencing batch reactor. *Enzyme Microb. Technol.* 39, 1392–1398. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enzmictec.2006.03.024>.

Cerqueira, V.R., Vaz Avelar De Carvalho, C., Sanches, E.G., Passini, G., Baloi, M., Rodrigues, R.V., 2017. Manejo de reprodutores e controle da reprodução de peixes marinhos da costa brasileira Broodstock management and control of reproduction in marine fishes of the Brazilian coast. *Rev. Bras. Reprod. Anim., Belo Horizonte* 41, 94–102.

Chopin, T., Buschmann, A.H., Halling, C., Troell, M., Kautsky, N., Neori, A., Kraemer, G. P., Zertuche-González, J.A., Yarish, C., Neefus, C., 2001. Integrating seaweeds into marine aquaculture systems: a key toward sustainability. *J. Phycol.* 37, 975–986. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1529-8817.2001.01137.x>.

Crab, R., Defoirdt, T., Bossier, P., Verstraete, W., 2012. Biofloc technology in aquaculture: Beneficial effects and future challenges. *Aquaculture* 356–357, 351–356. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2012.04.046>.

Da Silva, E.M., Sampaio, L.A., Martins, G.B., Romano, L.A., Tesser, M.B., 2013. Desempenho zootécnico e custos de alimentação de juvenis de tainha submetidos à restrição alimentar. *Pesqui. Agropecu. Bras.* 48, 906–912. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0100-204X2013000800014>.

David, F.S., Proença, D.C., Valenti, W.C., 2017. Phosphorus budget in integrated multitrophic aquaculture systems with Nile Tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus*, and Amazon River Prawn, *Macrobrachium amazonicum*. *J. World Aquac. Soc.* 48, 402–414. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jwas.12404>.

Ebeling, J.M., Timmons, M.B., Bisogni, J.J., 2006. Engineering analysis of the stoichiometry of photoautotrophic, autotrophic, and heterotrophic removal of ammonia-nitrogen in aquaculture systems. *Aquaculture* 257, 346–358. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2006.03.019>.

Ekasari, J., Angela, D., Hadi, S., Harris, E., Bossier, P., De Schryver, P., 2014. The size of biofloc determines the nutritional composition and the nitrogen recovery by aquaculture animals. *Aquaculture* 426–427, 105–111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2014.01.023>.

Figuerola, L.A., Silverstein, J., 1992. The effect of particulate organic matter on biofilm nitrification. *Water Environ. Res.* 64, 728–733. <https://doi.org/10.2175/WER.64.5.10>.

Furtado, P.S., Poersch, L.H., Wasielesky, W., 2014. The effect of different alkalinity levels on *Litopenaeus vannamei* reared with biofloc technology (BFT). *Aquac. Int.* 23, 345–358. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10499-014-9819-x>.

Gaona, C.A.P., Poersch, L.H., Krummenauer, D., Foes, G.K., Wasielesky, W.J., 2011. The effect of solids removal on water quality, growth and survival of *Litopenaeus vannamei* in a biofloc technology culture system. *Int. J. Recirc. Aquac.* 12, 54–73. <https://doi.org/10.21061/ijra.v12i1.1354>.

Gaona, C.A.P., de Almeida, M.S., Viau, V., Poersch, L.H., Wasielesky, W., 2017. Effect of different total suspended solids levels on a *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone, 1931) BFT culture system during biofloc formation. *Aquac. Res.* 48, 1070–1079. <https://doi.org/10.1111/are.12949>.

Ghosh, S., Ranjan, R., Megarajan, S., Pattnaik, P., Dash, B., Edward, L., 2016. Mixed culture of Pacific white shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone, 1931) and flathead grey mullet *Mugil cephalus* (Linnaeus, 1758) in floating cages. *Indian J. Fish* 63, 63–69. <https://doi.org/10.21077/ijf.2016.63.3.56378-08>.

Granada, L., Sousa, N., Lopes, S., Lemos, M.F.L., 2016. Is integrated multitrophic aquaculture the solution to the sectors' major challenges? – a review. *Rev. Aquac.* 8, 283–300. <https://doi.org/10.1111/raq.12093>.

Hargreaves, J.A., 2006. Photosynthetic suspended-growth systems in aquaculture. *J. Aquac. Eng. Fish. Res.* 34, 344–363. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaeng.2005.08.009>.

Hoang, M.N., Nguyen, P.N., Le, D.V.B., Nguyen, D.V., Bossier, P., 2018. Effects of stocking density of gray mullet *Mugil cephalus* on water quality, growth performance, nutrient conversion rate, and microbial community structure in the white shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* integrated system. *Aquaculture* 496, 123–133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2018.07.018>.

Jory, D.E., 2001. Feed management practices for a healthy pond environment. In: Browdy, C.L., Jory, C.L. (Eds.), *The NewWave, Proceedings of the Special Session on Sustainable Shrimp Culture*. TheWorld Aquaculture Society, Baton Rouge, LA, USA, pp. 118–143.

Kerrigan, D., Suckling, C.C., 2018. A meta-analysis of integrated multitrophic aquaculture: extractive species growth is most successful within close proximity to open-water fish farms. *Rev. Aquac.* 10, 560–572. <https://doi.org/10.1111/raq.12186>.

Krummenauer, D., Samocha, T., Poersch, L., Lara, G., Wasielesky, W., 2014. The reuse of water on the culture of pacific white shrimp, *litopenaeus vannamei*, in BFT system. *J. World Aquac. Soc.* 45, 3–14. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jwas.12093>.

Lara, G., Honda, M., Poersch, L., Wasielesky, W., 2017. The use of biofilm and different feeding rates in biofloc culture system: the effects in shrimp growth parameters. *Aquac. Int.* 25, 1959–1970. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10499-017-0151-0>.

Larson, E.T., Shanks, A.L., 1996. Consumption of marine snow by two species of juvenile mullet and its contribution to their growth. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 130, 19–28. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps130019>.

Legarda, E.C., Poli, M.A., Martins, M.A., Scheila Anelise Pereira, Martins, M.L., Machado, C., Lorenzo de, M.A., Vieira, F. de N., 2019. Integrated recirculating aquaculture system for mullet and shrimp using biofloc technology. *Aquaculture* 512, 734308. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2019.734308>.

Lin, Y.C., Chen, J.C., 2003. Acute toxicity of nitrite on *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone) juveniles at different salinity levels. *Aquaculture* 224, 193–201. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0044-8486\(03\)00220-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0044-8486(03)00220-5).

Martínez-Espineira, R., Chopin, T., Robinson, S., Noce, A., Knowler, D., Yip, W., 2015. Estimating the biomitigation benefits of integrated multi-trophic aquaculture: a contingent behavior analysis. *Aquaculture* 437, 182–194. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2014.11.034>.

Melo, E.P., Oshiro, L.M.Y., Fugimura, M.M.S., da Costa, T.V., Flor, Hdos R., Sant'ana, N. F., 2016. Monocultivo e policultivo do camarão *Litopenaeus schmitti* e do parati *Mugil curema* em sistema de bioflocos e água clara. *Bol. do Inst. Pesca* 42, 532–547. <https://doi.org/10.20950/1678-2305.2016v42n3p532>.

Naylor, R.L., Hardy, R.W., Bureau, D.P., Chiu, A., Elliott, M., Farrell, A.P., Forster, I., Gatlin, D.M., Goldburg, R.J., Hua, K., Nichols, P.D., 2009. Feeding aquaculture in an

- era of finite resources. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 106, 15103–15110. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0905235106>.
- Neori, A., Troell, M., Chopin, T., Yarish, C., Critchley, A., 2007. Environment : science and policy for sustainable development the need for a balanced ecosystem approach to blue revolution aquaculture. *Environment* 49, 37–41. <https://doi.org/10.3200/ENVT.49.3.36-43>.
- Oliveira, I.R., Soares, L.S.H., 1996. Alimentação da tainha *Mugil platanus* Günther, 1880 (Pisces: Mugilidae), da região estuarino-lagunas de Cananéia, São Paulo. *Brasil. Bol. Inst. Pesca* 23, 95–104.
- Perdikaris, C., Chrysafi, A., Ganiats, K., 2016. Environmentally friendly practices and perceptions in aquaculture: a sectoral case-study from a mediterranean-based industry. *Rev. Fish. Sci. Aquac.* 24, 113–125. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23308249.2015.1112358>.
- Poersch, L.H., Santos, M.H.S., Miranda-Filho, K.M., Wasielesky, W.J., 2007. Efeito agudo do nitrato sobre alevinos da tainha *Mugil platanus* (Pisces: Mugilidae). *Bol. Inst. Pesca, São Paulo* 33, 247–252.
- Poli, M.A., Legarda, E.C., De Lorenzo, M.A., Martins, M.A., Vieira, N., 2019. Pacific white shrimp and Nile tilapia integrated in a biofloc system under different fish-stocking densities. *Aquaculture* 498, 83–89.
- Ray, A.J., Lewis, B.L., Browdy, C.L., Leffler, J.W., 2010. Suspended solids removal to improve shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*) production and an evaluation of a plant-based feed in minimal-exchange, superintensive culture systems. *Aquaculture* 299, 89–98. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2009.11.021>.
- Reis, W.G., Wasielesky, W., Abreu, P.C., Brandão, H., Krummenauer, D., 2019. Rearing of the Pacific white shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone, 1931) in BFT system with different photoperiods: effects on the microbial community, water quality and zootechnical performance. *Aquaculture* 508, 19–29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2019.04.067>.
- Rocha, A.F.D.A., Abreu, P.C., Wasielesky, W., Tesser, M.B., 2012. Avaliação Da Formação De Bioflocos Na Criação De Juvenis De Tainha *Mugil Cf. Hospes* Sem Renovação De Água. *Atlântica* 34, 63–74. <https://doi.org/10.5088/atl.2012.34.1.63>.
- Samocha, T.M., Prangnell, D.I., 2019. Water quality management. *Sustain. Biofloc Syst. Mar. Shrimp* 133–151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-818040-2.00007-1>.
- Sampaio, L.A., Wasielesky, W., Campos Miranda-Filho, K., 2002. Effect of salinity on acute toxicity of ammonia and nitrite to juvenile *Mugil platanus*. *Bull. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.* 68, 668–674. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s001280306>.
- Shpigel, M., Ari, T., Ben, Shauli, L., Odintsov, V., Ben-Ezra, D., 2016. Nutrient recovery and sludge management in seabream and grey mullet co-culture in Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA). *Aquaculture* 464, 316–322. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2016.07.007>.
- Troell, M., Joyce, A., Chopin, T., Neori, A., Buschmann, A.H., Fang, J.G., 2009. Ecological engineering in aquaculture - Potential for integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA) in marine offshore systems. *Aquaculture* 297, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2009.09.010>.
- UNESCO, 1983. *Chemical Methods for Use in Marine Environmental Monitoring*. Paris, France, p. 53p.
- Vlaeminck, S.E., Terada, A., Smets, B.F., De Clippeleir, H., Schaubroeck, T., Bolea, S., Demeestere, L., Mast, J., Boon, N., Carballa, M., Verstraete, W., 2010. Aggregate size and architecture determine microbial activity balance for one-stage partial nitrification and anammox. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 76, 900–909. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.02337-09>.
- Wasielesky, W., Atwood, H., Stokes, A., Browdy, C.L., 2006. Effect of natural production in a zero exchange suspended microbial floc based super-intensive culture system for white shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei*. *Aquaculture* 258, 396–403. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2006.04.030>.
- Zar, J.H., 2010. *Biostatistical Analysis*. Prentice Hall, Upper Saddle River.